

EFFECT OF ENGLISH AND HAUSA LANGUAGES ON BASIC ADULT EDUCATION LEARNERS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN SOCIAL STUDIES IN CONTINUING EDUCATION INSTITUTE, MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

This study was conducted to determine the Effect of English and Hausa Languages on Basic Adult Education Learners' Academic Performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. The study had three objectives, three corresponding research questions and three hypotheses. The design of the study is quasi-experimental research design, involving pre-test and post-test treatment. The target population for the study was (48) forty eight adult Learners who are currently studying in Basic Adult Education Programme in the 2016/2017 session at Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri. The instruments used for data collection was a twenty items (20) objectives test in English, twenty items (20) objectives test in Hausa language and (20) objectives test in combined English and Hausa. The data collected was analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation, T-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The findings of the study showed that; the mean performance in Social Studies taught in Hausa and English languages was highest, followed by those taught in Hausa and those taught in English language. There is significant difference in performance of learners taught in Hausa language. There is significant difference in performance of learners taught in English language. There is significant difference in performance of learners taught in Hausa and English combined. Based on the findings of the study the following Recommendations were made among others: that the use of both English and Hausa Languages combined should be encouraged in teaching Social Studies in the Institute.

Keywords: basic adult education, effect, English, Hausa language, academic performance, social studies

1. Introduction

Language is the most important means by which a person (learns) to communicate or organize his/her experiences and thoughts. (Adebayo, 1995) stated that human language is one of the many means by which a person's experiences and thoughts can be organized. This support many senses that language has. Communication is the major bridge that links the whole world. Language is not everything in education but without language everything is nothing in education (Wolff, 2006). In a paper presented at Annual International Interdisciplinary Conference, (2013) stated that the importance of language is to promote social interaction and national cohesion; and preservation of cultures. Hence, every child has to learn the language of the immediate environment.

Adult learner is a person, male or female, who for some reason, seeks to learn either in school or outside the school. The adult learner may seek to learn to solve a personal problem or for some other reasons. As for our literacy learners, they are people who attend classes or some form of provision to learn or improve their literacy skills and general knowledge. (Okenimkpe, 2003) defines Adult learner as a person that has physiological, mental, economical and social issues, as well as his maturity that makes him different from the child in learning. As people aged, there is deterioration in the five senses of sight, hearing, taste, skin, and vision progressively become slower and less effective. This natural occurrence must also be considered and effectively managed for the adult to learn successfully. The other aspects that must be considered are the several roles that an adult by virtue of his adulthood occupies. He/she is an individual, spouse, parent, worker, member of a community, among others. Any or all of these could also constitute a problem at any point in the adult's learning life and must there by seen as a possible deterrent factor to learning if adequate care is not taken. The general dwindling speed of respond to stimulus is also exacerbated by memory problems (short and long term memory).The learning adult is ambivalent, doubtful of his ability, anxious, among others and needs reassurance as well as motivation. Other contributing factors and as reiterated by Kidd cited in (Okenimkpe, 2003) in the adult learning activities includes the following: strong motivation must be created, individual pace of learning must be respected, adult be carried along and familiarized with evaluation outcomes immediately, environmental factors that distract or inhibit learning must be eliminated or minimized, and learners must be encouraged to be self-directing.

In a multilingual society like Nigeria, a large number of indigenous languages exists and the number has been put differently, (Harford, 1986) mentioned 395 languages, Ayilara and Oyedeji, (2000) estimated 500 languages while (Bamgbose, 1992) maintains that it is 513 languages (Makinde, 2007). Despite this large number, English remains the official national language and as a result the generality of the population is unchanged towards oral use of English language. Practically, in the school system, English language has become the pre-eminent language of time to the present as it is the medium of instruction right from nursery school and throughout school life.

Exclusively, English is taught as a subject at all levels. While the indigenous languages largely are mostly restricted to their domain or regions of use.(Adegbija, 2004) Stated that of all the indigenous languages, only three have been recognized to be taught within the school system that is Yoruba, Hausa, and Igbo largely for socio-political relevance. Iyamu and Ogiegbaen (2005), are of the view that Mother tongue is normally understood as a language that is naturally learned by members of a speech community and is employed as the first medium of vocalized communication. It could be understood as the language of a native community or of a group with common ancestry. Therefore, each of the diverse ethnic communities in the world has its own language that is naturally learned by members in the socialization process (Blake, 2004).

Usman, (2003) stated that it may be true to say that, so many countries around the world and even in Africa use their own indigenous language to formulate educational policies and system for example , Egypt, China, Bulgaria, Germany and so on. In these countries, science subjects, arts and social sciences are taught in their Local Language. It is for this reason that most of those who go to these countries for studies have to spend some time learning the language of the country before going into their chosen field of studies.

According to Greenberg (1963), Hausa language belongs to the Chadic family which is a sub-group of Afro-Asiatic phylum. Speakers of the language are found in Nigeria, Niger, Ghana, Togo, Mali, Benin, Cameroon, Libya, Central Africa, and Equatorial Guinea in Africa and Saudi Arabia in Middle East. The language is spoken by over thirty five (35) million people in Africa alone (Zaria, 1982).

English language is a medium of communication widely used. It was introduced into Nigeria through the influence of British traders, missionaries and colonialists. Bamgbose, (1971) said that it was the most important heritage left behind at the end of the British era. English language in Nigeria is a second language (L2). It is a second language because Nigerians already had their first language or mother tongue (L1) before the advent of English into the country. In this instance, a foreign language (English) left its native environment and met with other language or languages (Nigerian indigenous languages), and changed the language of instruction into English in schools.

Ezegbe, (2008) defines Social Studies as a subject that aims at helping students who are creative, patriotic, and responsible and are able to contribute to the development of a nation. The Comparative Education Study and Adaption Centre (CESAC,1982) defines Social Studies as a subject that is considered with the way people live and interact with their social and physical environments and how science and technology help them to live well in those environments. CESAC went further to state the usefulness of social studies as a subject that helps the society to understand social problems and thereby helps to seek solution to the problem. In essence, social studies provide a way of understanding the society in order to understand its structure, its problems and to look for ways of solving those problems. It can therefore be claimed that the concern of social studies is to provide adult learners with knowledge of the

history, geography, social and political institutions and perhaps the psychological intricacies of daily existence in Nigeria. What distinguishes social studies from other disciplines is its ability to extract some basic concepts that enable adult learners to understand their fellow citizens holistically.

Okojie, (2005) supportively maintained that the ultimate goal of Social Studies is to equip individuals with knowledge and understanding for effective relationships and living. Due to its usefulness in national development, it has gained wide acceptance to the extent of becoming one of the core subjects at the Basic Adult Education Programme. Oluikpe (1984) recognizes this fact and notes that *"when we fail to communicate effectively, we fail to impact whatever ideas and knowledge we wish to contribute to humanity."* This implies that language is an amazing tool that helps in digging deep the understanding of social studies. Hence, in order to learn or study any other subject successfully, one need to have a language in one's control to enhance effective understanding of the subject one engages himself/herself to study which includes social studies. Considering all these facts, we therefore want to give attention to how well or how adult instructors work to improve their worth in the use of Hausa language in teaching social studies, the use of English language in teaching social studies and the use of both English and Hausa languages in teaching social studies in Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri, Borno State.

According to Fanon, (1964), to speak a language means to assume the culture of the native speakers of that language. The question arising is thus, which culture is being supported by Nigerian English teaching in classrooms? How effective is English as a language of instruction and cultural transmission in a multi-cultural context? This brings about the concept of the culture of the learners as well as English-speaking cultures. Bunyi, (1999) observes that for the goal of teaching African cultural values to be achieved, indigenous languages should be given a central place in education; otherwise, schools will be fostering in their children the values of the native speakers of English. Those who are in favor of the inclusion of foreign language culture in language classrooms argue that culture in language classrooms cannot be separated from one another. Byram and Fleming (1998), claims that the culture of the foreign language should be involved in language teaching for a full understanding of the language forms that are presented to learners, since it provides learners with a holistic view about how and when to use the language. (Mckay, 2013), on the other hand, emphasizes the involvement of the learner's local culture in a foreign language classroom.

The National Policy on Education revised (1981), buttresses the importance of mother tongue in teaching / learning process. As stated in the policy, the medium of instruction at primary 1-3 should be mother tongue or the language of immediate community. Emphasis was placed on indigenous languages as a medium of instruction in educational institutions as well as a means of preserving people's culture. Language is seen as an instrument per excellence and it stands for maintaining national unity.

In Borno State, there are many tribes and the state is therefore a multilingual with tribes like: Bura, Chinade, Chekede, Chinde, Chibok, Fulani, Glavda, Gava,

Hambagda, Hausa, Kanuri, Kanakuru, Kwayam, Mandara, Marghi, Shuwa, Terawa, Wala and Zilavda Languages. English language, therefore, is a second language (L2) since the people have their indigenous languages. And Hausa language is an indigenous language (L1) or language of the environment being used in Borno State. It is used in day to day activities. English and Hausa are medium of instruction in schools like Continuing Education Institute, Maiduguri, Borno State. Similar trend is obtained in all socio-cultural groups in Nigeria. English language, however, is an (L1) in certain countries of the world like Denmark, Scotland, Australia, America and England.

Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri was established in the year 1973 by then North Eastern State government of Nigeria. Three of such institutions were planned to be built in the three provinces -Adamawa, Bauchi, and Borno with the aim of developing into full flagged institute of adult and non-formal education. It was named adult education centers and was put into shape in 1988. It started with two courses Basic and Introductory in Adult Education programme both of which lasts for nine (9) months. In the Basic Adult Education Programme the courses that are available are as follows :- psychology of Adult Education, social studies, foundation of Adult Education, Home Economics, Integrated science, Mathematics, English Language, Islamic Religious Knowledge, Christian Religious Knowledge and Organization and Management. While in Introductory Adult Education, the courses that are available in the programme are Hausa Language, Integrated Science, English Language, Functional Literacy, Psychology of Adult Education, Community Development, Social Studies, Home Economics, Mathematics, Christian Religious Knowledge and Islamic Religious Knowledge.

With the takeoff of the Agency for mass literacy in the state in 1988, and also in pursuance of the ongoing Federal Government accelerated Mass Literacy Campaign Programme and intensive rural development programme in which Borno State like any other state in the federation is actively participating, during the late 1980s and early 1990s Basic and Introductory Adult Education courses were undertaken in Hausa language to train more knowledgeable and competent front-line staff (scheme or organizers or village level authorities in various local government Areas and instructors) and also convert the existing unqualified instructors and supervisors to be qualified as they were directly involved in translating and extending the Agency's programme closer to the door steps of the target group.

In the present day situation, in Basic Adult Education programme, English language is used in teaching and learning. The beneficiaries are those people that completed one year introductory course which will lead them to one year Basic Adult Education and those that are junior secondary school drop-outs are enrolled to Basic, after Basic one year, they will move to remedial studies at the end, they will write S.S.C.E, so as to have S.S.C.E. Certificate. Hence, this led to the upgrading of the Institute in 1989 with the modification and expansion of its academic programmes, in which as a result, certificate courses were introduced. Namely, Certificate in Adult Education and Certificate in Home Economics. And later certificates in Community

Development, Extension Services and Personal Development were awarded. And now, the Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri, Borno State have nine (9) Departments or Programmes namely: Diploma in Adult Education, Certificate in Adult Education, Diploma in Political Education and Administration, Certificate in Political Education and Administration, Diploma in Computer, Certificate in Computer, Diploma in Business Administration and Management, Certificate in Business Administration and Management, Diploma in Social Work, Certificate in Social Work, Diploma in Home Economics, Certificate in Home Economics, Diploma in Arabic and Islamic Studies, Certificate in Arabic and Islamic Studies, Basic Adult Education, Introductory Adult Education and Remedial Studies. The purpose is to acquaint the students with the necessary theoretical knowledge and techniques that will enable them carry out their professional duties as education practitioners effectively. It is also meant to expose the learners to the various modern approaches, ideas in administration, process of adult education and Home-Economics; and to equip them with the necessary practical experience which will enable them become better adult educators.

Academic performance is conceived as the scholastic standing of the student at a given period. This could be accounted for uniform grades obtained in examination on a course or group of courses. According to (Shuaibu, 1993), academic performance is the process where student's educational activities are measured by examinations within the context of a curriculum. According to Graetz, (1995), one's educational success depends very strongly on socio economic status of the parents. (Considine and Zappal 2002), argued that families where the parents are advantaged socially, educationally and economically foster a high level of achievement in their children. The researchers agree with (Considine and Zappal's, 2002) view because students or learners from high socio economic backgrounds are well exposed to scholastic materials which aid their intelligence. However, events have shown that Adult learners' performance in Social Studies while taught in English is below expectation from five years record in Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri, Borno State, in year 2011-2012 session, out of 53 learners 75% failed while 25% passed. In 2012-2013 session, out of 68 learners 70% failed while 30% passed, while in 2013-2014 session, out of 43 learners, 70% failed while 30% passed. In 2014-2015 session out of 62 learners 90% failed while 10% passed and in 2015-2016 sessions out of 58 learners, 89% failed while 11% passed (Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri, 2017).

Wolff, (2006) reported that language is not everything in Education but without language, everything is nothing in education. Although some researchers have carried out investigations on this problem of mother tongue interference in Nigeria, their main focus has been on the three major Nigerian languages; Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa. Studies of this kind have not been carried out on adult learners in Continuing Education Institute, Maiduguri, Borno State.

The aim of this study, therefore, is to look at the adult learners' academic performance in order to compare their academic performance in the use of Hausa in teaching Social Studies and in the use of English Language in teaching Social Studies

and in the use of both English and Hausa Languages in teaching Social Studies. Those factors that could contribute to either learners' academic success or failure include among others: their attitudes to learning and their interest in academic pursuance.

2. Statement of the Problem

In a multilingual society like Nigeria, a large number of indigenous languages exist and the number has been put differently. It was reported by (Bamgbose, 1992) that there are 513 languages in Nigeria, despite this large number, English remains the official national language and as a result, the generality of the population is unchanged, towards oral use of English language. This has been a serious concern to the researchers. The researchers have observed that the performance of Basic Adult Education learners in Social Studies has been poor, in the Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri. One of the things that may influence performance of the learners is language of instruction. The language of instruction has been English language; this study intends to determine the Effect of teaching Social Studies in Hausa, English and in both English and Hausa languages combined.

2.1 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to determine:

- i. effect of Hausa language on learners Academic Performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria
- ii. effect of English Language on learners' Academic Performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria
- iii. effect of English and Hausa Languages combined on learners Academic Performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria

2.2 Research Questions

The following research questions were answered:

- i. Do adult learners perform better when Social Studies is taught in Hausa?
- ii. Do adult learners perform better when Social Studies is taught in English?
- iii. Do adult learners perform better when Social Studies is taught using both Hausa and English Languages?

2.3 Hypotheses

The study tested the following hypotheses:

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the performance of learners taught in Hausa language

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the performance of learners taught in English language

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the performance of learners taught in Hausa and English language.

2.4 Significance of the Study

It is expected that the result of the study will benefit the adult learners, Instructors, the management of the Institute; it will also assist the stakeholders in restructuring the policy to a pattern that will improve the learners' performance in the programme. The finding of this study will be an additional contribution to the existing knowledge. It will also serve as a valuable source of materials and guide for future researchers.

2.5 Scope of the Study

The study was carried out in Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri, Borno State and it covered adult learners who are registered under the 2016/2017 session for Basic Adult Education Programme at Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri, Borno State. The study is also delimited to the Effect of Hausa Language on Learners Academic performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria, Effect of English Language on Learners Academic Performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria and Effect of English and Hausa Languages combined on learners Academic Performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

3. Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design, pre-test and post-test treatment were used using mean, standard deviation, T-test and Analysis of variance (ANOVA) which determined the performance of adult learners when taught in Hausa language, English and both English and Hausa languages. The target population for the study was 55 adult learners that are studying in Basic Adult Education Programme 2016/2017 session in Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri, Borno State. The sample for the study was 48 adult learners randomly selected using simple sampling technique. The research instrument for this study were A pre and post test questions consisting of 4 sections; A, B, C, and D. Section A Demographic data, B. English items, C. Hausa Language items, D. Combination of English and Hausa Languages item. A sixteen item questionnaire to (i). test adult learners performance in Social Studies taught in English; (ii). test adult learners performance in Social Studies taught in Hausa and (iii). To test adult learners performance in Social Studies taught in both English and Hausa languages combined.

Experts in Research and statistics at the Departments of: Education and Continuing Education and Extension Services University of Maiduguri were consulted for the face and content validity of the instrument. This is to ascertain the validity of the instrument in terms of the language of presentation, clarity and applicability to the level of the adult learners that were involved in the study. The responses of these experts

were to produce the final instrument. The reliability test was conducted using the instrument, on adult learners that are not part of this work. Before conducting the research, a reliability test was conducted with 10 respondents that did not participate in the study using test-re-test method which gave a reliability coefficient of 0.73, indicating the instrument is strong enough to carry out the study.

Research assistants were trained and used. They are some of the Social Studies and Hausa Language teachers in the school selected for the study. They helped in the treatment exercises of the research. The experimental groups were instructed in Hausa, Social Studies in English and the control groups were instructed in both English and Hausa Languages in teaching Social Studies throughout the period of the research. Teaching and learning activities lasted for four weeks. Finally, post-test were administered to the three groups; scripts collected and scored accordingly after the exercise. The scores served as data for the work.

The research treatment procedures were in five phases as follows; Preliminary stage, pre-treatment stage, treatment stage, revision/correction stage and post-treatment stage. This took whole week. With the help of research assistants, the pre-treatment test was administered. The treatment took four weeks using instructional guides to the subjects followed by a week of revision. This is summarized as follows:

Table 1: Time Table for Treatment Procedure

Week	Activity	Stage
1 st	Researchers introduced themselves and recruited research Assistant in the sample institute	Preliminary
2 nd	Administration of pre-test	Pre-treatment
3 rd -5 th	Instruction/teaching experimental groups, We taught the Basic Adult learners who are currently studying in the institute 2016/2017 session. Social studies were taught based on their syllabus in the class daily for the period of four weeks and a lesson plan, the topics taught were Basic concepts of Social Studies, Physical Environment, Marriage, types of marriage, Contentment, Societal Values and Child Abuse in Continuing Education Institute, the adult learners are in their first semester.	.. Treatment
6 th	Revision/correction	
7 th	Administration of test items	Post-test

The statistical techniques that were used were mean, standard deviation, T-test and Analysis of variance (ANOVA) which permitted the measurement of three or more variables for comparison.

3.1 Data Analysis

Research question 1: Do adult learners perform better when Social Studies is taught in Hausa?

Table 2 shows The Mean, Standard Deviation, T-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Adult learners Academic performance in Hausa, English language and both English and Hausa languages.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Language of Instruction	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
Hausa	85.9	8.0	70	100
English	60.9	19.9	25	90
Hausa/English	91.6	8.7	70	100

Table 2 shows that mean performance of adult learners' academic performance when Social Studies was taught in Hausa language is 85.9 with standard deviation of 8.0. The minimum performance is 70 and maximum performance of 100.

Research question 2: Do adult learners perform better when Social Studies is taught in English?

The data in table 2 show that the mean performance of adult learners' academic performance when Social Studies was taught in English is 60.9 with standard deviation of 19.9. The minimum performance is 25.0 and maximum performance of 90.

Research question 3: Do adult learners perform better when Social Studies is taught using both English and Hausa languages? The mean performance is 91.6 with standard deviation of 8.7. The minimum performance is 70 and maximum of 100.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the performance of learners taught in Hausa.

Table 3: T-test of the performance of Hausa

T	d f	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
4.655	30	.000	Significant

Table 3 above describes the test carried out for the performance of Learners in Hausa. From the result, it was observed that at $t=4.655$, there is a significant difference in the performance of the Learners in the two languages, $P<0.0<0.05$. Hence this implies that there is a significant difference in performance of the Learners when taught in the two languages.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the performance of learners taught in English.

Table 4: T-test of the performance of English

T	d f	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
-1.903	30	.067	Not significant

Table 4 describes the relationship or the difference between the uses of English. The result shows that at $t(-1.903)$ there was a $p > 0.06 > 0.05$ which implies that there is significant difference in the use English in teaching Social Studies.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the performance of learners taught in English and Hausa Languages combined.

Table 5: T-test of the performance of Hausa taught group and English language group

T	d f	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
-5.632	30	.000	Significant

Shows that the significant difference exist between Hausa and English p-value 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, at $t = -5.632$.

Table 6: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	d.f	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	8504.167	2	4252.083	23.746	.000
Within Groups	8057.813	45	179.063		
Total	16561.979	47			

Table 6 shows the differences between and within the performance of the Learners, in the use of all the languages, the result shows at F (23, 746) There is a P-value and $P < 0.05 < 0.05$, which means that there is a significant difference in performance of the Learners when the two languages are used but there is no significant difference in the performance when a combination of the two languages were used.

4. Findings

The result of the data analyzed showed that: the mean performance in Social Studies taught in Hausa and English language was highest, followed by those taught in Hausa and those taught in English language. There is significant difference in performance of learners taught in Hausa language. There is significant difference in performance of learners taught in English language. There is significant difference in performance of learners taught in Hausa and English combined.

5. Discussion

The study was carried out to determine the Effect of English and Hausa Languages on Basic Adult Education Learners' Academic Performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute Maiduguri, Borno State. Nigeria. The mean Academic performance in Social Studies taught in Hausa and English languages was highest, followed by those taught in English language.

Ogunmi and Owolabi, (2013) earlier found that there is no significant difference in the performance of the students exposed to the use of mother tongue in mathematics that shows that f -calculated (0.295) is less than f -table (2.99) at 0.05 level of significance. Abdu, (2011) revealed that teachers experience has an impact on pupils' performance in primary mathematics. Contrast to the finding of Ogunmi and Owolabi (2013) that finding on the Effect of Hausa language on learners Academic Performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute, shows that at $t=4.655$, there is significant difference in the performance of the student.

Aina's and Olanipekun (2013) showed there is no significant difference of English language on students' academic performance. The finding is also in contrast to Abubakar's study of (2005) that the English language has effect on all the other subjects of the curriculum at the secondary school level because it is the official language of instruction. More so, contrast to the finding of Aina's and Olanipekun (2013) on the Effect of English Language on learners Academic Performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. There is no significant difference in the use of English language, the result shows that at $t(-1.902)$ there was a $p > 0.06 > 0.05$.

Patrick and Theresa, (2005) submitted earlier that primary 3 pupils who were taught mathematics in Igbo language had higher mean retention level scores than their male counterparts taught in English language. Ezeudo and Obiageli, (2011) the students' taught with Igbo language had a higher mean score than those taught with English language, which mean that those taught with Igbo language achieved better than those taught in English language. The result shows that there is significant effect due to Igbo language on students' achievement in integrated science (BSAT). This finding is in line with other works done by Ehindero, (1980), Olarewaju and Akinwumi, (1980) Jimoh and Salawa, (1998). The work is not in line with the research done by Umo, (2001) in which the game strategy was not a significant factor on the student's achievement in Igbo. The effect of English and Hausa languages combined on learners' Academic Performance in Social Studies in Continuing Education Institute, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. The finding is in line with Patrick and Theresa (2005) shows that significant difference exists in English and Hausa, p -value 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, $t=5.632$.

Oribabor and Adesina, (2013) in their study on Students' Academic Performance in English and Hausa languages found that, there is no significant difference between English and Hausa Languages performance, found out that the pupils taught in mother tongue performed better than the groups taught in English language. Oribabor and Adesina (2013) shows contrast in the performance in English and Hausa Languages shows that significant difference exist in English and Hausa, P -value 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05, $t=5.632$.

6. Conclusion

Based on the results of the findings, the study concludes that the use of Hausa Language and English and Hausa Languages combined in teaching Social Studies in the Institute helps adult learners perform better.

6.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made that the use of both English and Hausa languages combined should be encouraged in teaching Social Studies in the Institute.

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